

Foreign Economic Relations of Azerbaijan and the Geopolitical Perspectives of Its Development under Modern Conditions

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Abstract:

The aim of scientific research is to identify the prospects for foreign economic relations and the continued development of geopolitical interests in the world, increase foreign investment, develop competitive national wealth, uncover the essence and recreate a real picture of foreign economic relations. Considering the growing pace of development of diplomatic and economic relations between the countries of the world, it predetermines the need to create new forms of foreign economic relations of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: international economic development model; foreign economic activity; foreign investment; elimination of need; economic solidarity; international cooperation; geopolitical realities.

Introduction

With the development of economic relations between the diplomatic and the creation of new forms of external communication, the economic goal of the countries of the world becomes necessary. The economic growth of each country depends to a large extent on the level of their foreign economic relations. At the same time, foreign economic relations depend on the nature of the world geopolitical environment.

No country, even in spite of its powerful economy, cannot develop at the proper level. [1]. at the same time, foreign economic relations, the history of mankind to achieve the current situation was a very difficult road. Thus, the development of society, social community, slavery, feudalism, capitalism entered the modern world through stages.

The Course of the Study

In ancient Egypt, gradually began a stage in the economic development of modern economic relations and the establishment of diplomatic relations between the peoples achieved. Many classical works of ancient Egypt were formed before the celebration of statehood in spite of Athens, as well as the ancient formation in the territory of Azerbaijan in

political and economic relations was emphasized. Foreign economic relations, the development of the social division of labor, the specialization of production and economic conditions of life.

The development of foreign economic relations predetermines the social division of labor, the specialization of production and the economic conditions of life internationalization. There are different views on approaches to addressing this issue.

another us president, theodore roosevelt, noted that "from ancient times - and now even more than before - managed and controlled the world of secret societies, in the first place. Policy mismatch. If something happened, this is also thought. "[5] however, some economists controversial views, arguing that theodore roosevelt in 1907 at the us congress, said that "natural resources, unreasoned, irrational and cruel use of, exploitation as a result of their destruction, leading the earth to destruction leads and so the development of the prosperity of our economy, and is also the cause of sustainable artımaına impact over time, harmful consequences for future generations, "he said.

theodore roosevelt approach the controversial event in his rejection of admiral's economic ideas, a. marsal preferred the psychological development of subjective aspects to the approach and this was proved by the world economic system. One of the theories put forward in the field of international economic relations a. smitin " the theory of absolute advantage. "While attaching great importance to the principle of comparative costs and benefits from international trade, according to a.smitin, is the international division of labor and specialization, and also international trade in the world economy becomes richer at the expense of the development of individual countries; closed countries in the world economy and international trade, refusing to be more profitable.

Compared with other countries, which is the highest of any commercial quality necessarily can produce cheaper, then this country has been deemed advisable specialization in the production of goods. Goods are not necessarily that has an advantage in the production and export of the country, is limited to its development, he said. [6] it is these principles that are effective economic relations that are one of the main conditions for ensuring social and economic progress.

Statistical analysis in the context of globalization in 200 countries shows that this is an objective process. Nevertheless, geopolitical advantages after the Second World War, the leading countries of the world, the United States began to penetrate into russian-turkish relations and economic competition plays an important role in the development of foreign policy and economic relations. in 1947, with the participation of 23 countries, including the us gatt (general agreement on tariffs and trade) - the signing of the general agreement on tariffs and economic relations with world economic and political relations between the important and productive period. [4]

At the same time, heydar aliyeu in the development of foreign economic relations of our country's integration into the world economy in the years 1970-1985 is an important stage in the development of the description; he noted that serious errors were given in previous years, the deployment of production forces.

At the end of the last century, the collapse of the socialist system of the Soviet Union failed the endings and led to the formation of a new world order. Recently, an independent country at the time, as in other areas of foreign and economic policy, was a mess. Azerbaijan's national leader heydar aliyeu started a new era in the history of foreign economic relations in the life of the country. As a result of his serious efforts to change the situation in the region and around the world, positive changes have been possible.

The head of successive visits to foreign countries, representatives of international organizations, at meetings, thanks to successful diplomatic activity, even under the influence of the pressure of armenian aggression against Azerbaijan, the socio-economic situation in the country and told the world community of truth about the economic potential. [3].

From the commonwealth of independent states was one of the first steps in this direction. when organizing the former soviet republics, he worked consistently to strengthen bilateral and multilateral relations. countries in the field of economy, trade and cultural cooperation were given special attention. [2].

Azerbaijan attaches great importance to the development of foreign economic relations with russia. Strengthening friendly relations between the two countries and playing a special role of the national leader heydar aliyeu.

The world's most powerful country and is constantly on the rise in building relations with the us in the development of heydar aliyeu's services priceless. Independent Azerbaijan and two countries established diplomatic relations in 1992. But this is only the first step. This is the way forward, a number of issues for clarification, expansion, confidence, trust, work hard to represent Azerbaijan, big show diplomatic activities are required. [3].

In this regard, 1994 was a turning point in the relations between Azerbaijan and the west. thus, to Azerbaijan, economic cooperation with our country, to its problems, there was an interest in geopolitical significance for it.

this interest was expressed by the united states by recognizing the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan, it became an ally of the settlement of conflict problems through a peaceful settlement. thus, Azerbaijan and economic cooperation with our country and its problems, had an interest in geopolitical significance. in a short time, as a result of heydar aliyeu's

targeted foreign economic policy, the most influential countries in the world-the united states, russia, Egypt, britain, germany, france, italy, etc. have established strong foreign economic relations with Azerbaijan.

Today our country passes through the transport corridors north-south and east-west, as well as strengthening cooperation in the field of foreign economic relations and bring economic dividends for our countries. we will also be able to implement projects in the neighboring countries of the cis member states in the future.

The deputy head of the presidential administration, nowruz mammadov, noted in his interview that it is difficult to find the second such balanced attitude of the country in the former soviet union that, in order to maintain its stability for 25 years. He was created by the great leader heydar aliyev and continues with president ilham aliyev. The basis of domestic and foreign policy of the country is strong.

Despite the difficult geographical location in the region, it has been possible to establish relations in all directions and is able to keep it in the future.

The big powers want to gain prestige in the world; small countries should settle disputes fairly. She also gives them a strong confidence in trusting us. The issue of the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan should be reflected in all documents. Nevertheless, i regret those who accuse the country to use all opportunities. Our position is very clear. Who is the aggressor, and who is the victim of aggression enough to look at the map of the region. Therefore, as you know, the world not only among equals becomes more stable. at the "v baku international humanitarian forum, a society in which the direction of the movement to understand the place of the world class," the head of the presidential administration, academician ramiz mehdiyev noted that internationalism and humanism, progress, civilization, tradition and naturally [3].

The structure of the economy of Azerbaijan in the times of the soviet union satisfied the needs of the national economy, and this was a situation that could not realize the advantages of the international division of labor. However, the former republics were formed in 1991-1994, as well as between enterprises, production and economic relations and the positive trade balance began to be destroyed. The production cooperation quickly fell.at the same time, this process reduced the volume of imports and exports by the end of 1997 on imports, the volume of exports until the third quarter of 1999 continued. This process also covered another area of foreign economic relations.

Thus, for the rapid development of foreign economic relations and progress in a number of areas, should be restored. at the same time, the expansion of foreign economic relations of the country's political and economic influence in the world, the growing success in all spheres of the economy, provides for the creation of pruning. in addition, in 2016, the seventh global forum of the alliance of civilizations of the united nations and influential countries of the world is a member of this organization and develop bilateral and multilateral cooperation in the field of the economy and geopolitical prospects of the country. the analysis shows that there is little difference in the growth rates of foreign economic relations between the two countries in in the long run, this creates differences in the level of economic development. For example, the average annual rate of economic growth in the years 1870-1985 in the us, 1.83%, 1.23%, while in the uk was.

Economic growth, which led him to a small difference of 115 years, gdp per capita in the united states than in the uk was 62%. Received a 2-fold increase in gdp in the united states from 40, 67 in the uk. However, the country's foreign economic relations have risen sharply, as the table below shows clearly.

Dynamics of Azerbaijan's foreign trade relations

Years	Trade turnover in millions of dollars.			US on the ratio of the previous year in%			
	Total	Import	Export	Saldo	Total	Import	Export
2005	8.558,4	4 301,2	4 347,2	136,0	120,0	119,8	120,2
2006	11.612,9	5 266,7	6 372,2	1.105,5	136,0	125,1	146,1
2007	11.771,7	5 713,0	6 058,2	344,7	101,1	108,5	94,1
2008	54.926,0	7 170,0	47 316,0	40.581,0	466,6	127,5	701,0
2009	20.824,5	6 123,1	14 701,4	8.578,3	36,9	81,4	30,9
2010	28.960,8	6 600,1	21 360,2	14.759,6	120,0	105,0	120,3
2011	41.161,7	9.756,0	31.405,7	24.649,7	104,0	133,1	92,6
2012	33.531,3	9.652,9	20.908,0	12.255,1	89,3	91,9	80,1
2013	43.554,1	10.712,3	32.841,6	22.129,1	102,7	109,1	100,7
2014	36.016,0	9.187,7	21.828,6	12.640,9	94,1	83,6	94,5

In 2015, the country produced 1.8 percent of gross domestic product, compared to the previous year amounted to 52.2 billion pounds. gdp per capita was us \$ 5003.2 pounds. 35.3 billion worth of non-oil sector of the economy, value-added products, its share in gdp increased from 69.3 percent. During this period, 33.93 percent of the gross domestic product in industry, 10 percent of trade, 6.23 percent in agriculture, 19.31 percent were obtained in other areas. Net taxes on products and imports of 8.19 percent of gdp.

in january-november 2015, the foreign trade turnover is 18.0 billion us dollars, including export of 10.6 billion \$ 8.2 billion dollars, and imports. With 2.3 billion us dollars. The positive balance of the us trade balance.

The cis countries, kazakhstan, 20 percent, 31 percent in georgia, armenia and the russian federation, 45 percent 18.0, but the economic measures taken by the above countries, then the devaluation took an average of 15 percent. In recent months, there has been an increase in the share of the devaluation of the money supply in the republic. the reason for this decline in the rate of manat in relation to the us dollar. Nevertheless, the above-mentioned currencies stabilized after the devaluation. However, in the present conditions of the policy of the country, the leader ilham aliyev, create a strong economy, strengthen the economic potential, exchange the foreign exchange rate to maintain stability and create new jobs, at the same time, focused on improving people's well-being. (4p.27)

it is very good that the socio-economic development of the country and the first developed the concept of economic relations and economic opportunities, primarily in different social strata of the population and its value, interests, traditions and aspirations should be carefully thought out knew. Most developed countries in the modern world, such a concept is definitely in people, not for the economy, the economy of people. Currently, developed countries, sustainable economic development, its structure, quantity and quality of human well-being as a goal to enrich and improve the quality of life of the car are considered as necessary for human development on a regular basis. Thus, developed countries in the world in comparison with other areas in the account of funds allocated for human potential are considered more effective.

Measures taken by the state play an important role in developing foreign economic relations. foreign economic relations, import-export; specialization of production at the international level; exchange of scientific and technical activities and their consequences; investments; migration of labor; tourism; participate in the activities of international economic organizations; includes the state regulation of the economy and other problems.

the national leader noted that "in all countries, as on an equal footing, relations with turkey, iran and neighboring georgia, russia and the united states, and the west, with the countries of the arab countries, muslim countries and the turkic states and the countries of central asia, .course of foreign economic relations affects the welfare of the population.

mr. president ilham aliyev noted that Azerbaijani citizens support our policy, strives to support our policy and sees that there is no alternative to our policy. An alternative policy would be a disaster; he can take in the abyss. Our policy in support of people in the referendum "yes," he said. i would like to thank them once again for the confidence and support of the people of Azerbaijan. [2]

As mr. ilham aliyev noted, the current situation of the external economic relations is different. i have repeatedly said that we live in an era of postneft.

Nevertheless, after several years of very large volumes of natural gas for export to the world market and the inflow of foreign currency will increase. but we live in such a way that the postneft period and in this case, of course, serious economic reforms were carried away.

Export promotion and attraction of investments are very large discounts. This is expanding in all areas of the reform; transparency must be ensured. in this case, we absolutely must exclude dependence on oil. for several years the state budget, the vast majority of the non-oil sector should be provided. in Azerbaijan, international events are held, which attract the attention of the whole world. For example, this year is the seventh global forum of the un alliance of civilizations. Around the world event. Of course, the race formula 1 takes a special place in the promotion of our country.

Analyzing the relationship, it becomes apparent that the volume of trade with the countries of the world for more than 10 years, 10.9 times and 15.2 times, including imports and exports 5.1. During the same period, imports exceeded exports. Balance 239.1 million 21500.0 million us dollars. Dollars increased.

There was an increase in turnover. Achievements in the field of geography and in the structure of foreign trade turnover have progressed. It was recorded from the statistical materials of 2000-2015. in this period, all with the countries of asia, 17.1 times, america, 150.1 times, africa and the countries of oceania, in 322.7 71.0 times exceeded. In import-export zones, establishment of trade relations between geographic regions, dynamic changes. [7]

Data analysis, as shown in our country, as in other areas of decisive measures was implemented in the direction of expanding foreign economic relations. Thus, the republic in 1991 82, 1992 64, 1995 69, 122 in 2000, 135 in 2005, 143 in 2006 and currently has 158 state and foreign economic relations. Import-export operations in Azerbaijan in 2015, analysis of relevant materials, unilaterally carried out the import operations of the republic with 43 countries (154805 thousand dollars.)

Export operations with 10 countries 1326.0 thousand dollars respectively). import and export operations in 96 countries (bilateral) (363100599 thousand dollars were equal, the study shows that the improvement of the structure of export-import operations and expansion of foreign economic relations.) all of the above confirms once again that Azerbaijan's foreign economic relations are built-in with all countries of the world operating and developing in this area of activity.

president ilham aliyev at a meeting of the cabinet of ministers dedicated to discussing the results of the social and economic development of the regions of the country for 9 months of 2016 and upcoming said: "... we get new partners around the world, and we see that in the world there is a great interest in cooperation with Azerbaijan in the field of non-traditional for us continents.

Especially here in latin america. we are building very good relations with the countries of latin america, and we see that this relationship is very sincere. mutual respect based on interest and friendship. relations with each country should be based on these principles. we have stated this many times. "

Conclusions

External economic relations of Azerbaijan in january-september 2016, individuals and legal entities, in 174 countries around the world, trade operations were carried out with partners from 103 countries of import and export of goods, 158 were imported into the country.

All these factors lead to the growing influence of the country in the world of foreign economic relations. i think that the achievements in the field of foreign economic relations of our country in the international arena, the increase of its role in the new world order, shows that Azerbaijan is on the right track.

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